

Quantum Electrodynamics (QED) Correction to the Klein-Nishina Formula

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Introduction

This work addresses a correction to the "classical" Klein-Nishina formula for the differential cross-section of Compton scattering, using Quantum Electrodynamics (QED) techniques. We consider the electron target almost at the rest and photon in X-ray domain.

Our goal is to improve the Klein-Nishina expression by incorporating self-energy corrections derived from one loop integrals. While the Klein-Nishina formula accurately describes the interaction of photons with electrons at low to moderate energies, higher-energy processes necessitate QED corrections to account for self-energy contributions. In this study, we explicitly include a logarithmic correction arising from the electron self-energy, leading to a slight but noteworthy improvement in the differential cross-section.

Methodology

The correction introduced in this work arises from the self-energy $\Sigma_1(p)$ of the electron, obtained through a QED **differential approach** based on the Schwinger-Dyson equations in their closed form (**Dyson equation**). These equations provide a non-perturbative framework for calculating propagators, such as the electron propagator $S_1(p)$, which is modified by the self-energy contributions.

In the most general form the Dyson equation may be written as $G = G_0 + G_0 \Sigma G$ where the zero subscript in the Green function refers to the free particle system and its formal resolution is given by $G = \frac{1}{G_0^{-1} - \Sigma}$.

In our the context, the first-order corrected propagator in the momentum space is then given by¹

$$S_1(p) = \frac{1}{\not{p} - m - \Sigma_1(p)}$$

where we use the free electron propagator $S_0(p) = \frac{1}{\not{p} - m - i\epsilon}$.

The self-energy $\Sigma_1(p)$ is derived as follow (the vertex function is kept in its simplest form):

$$\Sigma_1(p) = e^2 \int \frac{d^4k}{(2\pi)^4} \frac{\gamma^\mu (k + m) \gamma_\mu}{(k^2 - m^2 + i\eta)((p - k)^2 + i\eta)}$$

After performing dimensional regularization and a Wick rotation, we isolate the significant logarithmic term that includes the renormalization scale μ , leading to the following expression for the self-energy correction:

$$\Sigma_1(p) = \frac{e^2}{16\pi^2} (\not{p} + m) \ln\left(\frac{p^2}{\mu^2}\right)$$

¹ Unless otherwise specified, THESE natural units are assumed: $\hbar = c = 1$ and m stands for m_e .

It's now possible to evaluate the transition amplitude, from

$$\mathcal{M} = \bar{u}(p') \left[\gamma^\mu S_0(p) \gamma^\nu + \gamma^\mu S_0(p) \Sigma_1(p) S_1(p) \gamma^\nu \right] u(p)$$

$$\mathcal{M}_0 = e^2 \bar{u}(p') \gamma^\mu S_0(p) \gamma^\nu u(p)$$

$$\mathcal{M}_\Sigma = e^2 \bar{u}(p') \gamma^\mu S_0(p) \Sigma(p) S(p) \gamma^\nu u(p)$$

$$|\mathcal{M}|^2 = |\mathcal{M}_0 + \mathcal{M}_\Sigma|^2 = |\mathcal{M}_0|^2 + 2\Re(\mathcal{M}_0 \mathcal{M}_\Sigma^\dagger) + |\mathcal{M}_\Sigma|^2.$$

We then employ the differential scattering relation and the energy-momentum conservation, where the invariable s represents the Mandelstam variable for the center-of-mass energy, which is approximately (in our energy range) m^2 and θ is the photon scattering angle.

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \frac{1}{64\pi^2 s} \frac{1}{|\vec{k}|^2} |\mathcal{M}|^2$$

$$\frac{\omega'}{\omega} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{\omega}{m}(1 - \cos \theta)}$$

So we obtain, upon some calculations and simplification, the following full expression for the differential cross-section, where we used m as a natural renormalization scale².

$$\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} = \frac{e^4}{32\pi^2 m^2} \left(\frac{\omega'}{\omega} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega'} + \frac{\omega'}{\omega} - \sin^2 \theta \right) + \frac{e^4}{64\pi^2 m^2} \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega'} + \cos \theta \right) \left[\ln \left(\frac{p_e^2}{m^2} \right) + \ln^2 \left(\frac{p_e^2}{m^2} \right) \right]$$

² In this work, μ has been chosen to coincide with the mass of the electron m_e , as usual in on-shell renormalisation. This avoids the introduction of the term related to the Euler-Mascheroni constant, keeping the logarithmic contributions in $\ln(p_e^2/m_e^2)$ consistent.

Final Result

Replacing $\frac{e^4}{16\pi^2 m_e^2}$ with the square of the classical electron radius r_e ³ one realizes that the first term originating from the free amplitude is identical to the Klein-Nishina formula and the others terms represents the usually QED logarithmic expression deriving from the one loop electron self-energy correction.

To account for the comparison with the formula obtained by Klein and Nishina, we made a couple of numerical estimates from X-photons of energy 10 KeV that are scattered by electrons with 0.55 MeV and 1.00 MeV, respectively.

$$\Delta \left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right)_{\text{loop}} \simeq \frac{r_e^4}{4} \left[\ln \left(\frac{p_e^2}{m^2} \right) + \ln^2 \left(\frac{p_e^2}{m^2} \right) \right]$$

$$\left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right)_{\text{K-N}} \simeq \frac{r_e^2}{2} \simeq \frac{7.94 \times 10^{-26}}{2} \simeq 3.97 \times 10^{-26} \text{ cm}^2/\text{sterad}$$

$$\Delta \left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right)_{\text{loop0.55MeV}} \simeq \frac{7.94 \times 10^{-26}}{4} \times 0.1725 \simeq 3.44 \times 10^{-27} \text{ cm}^2/\text{sterad}$$

$$\Delta \left(\frac{d\sigma}{d\Omega} \right)_{\text{loop1MeV}} \simeq \frac{7.94 \times 10^{-26}}{16} \times 1.17 \simeq 5.82 \times 10^{-27} \text{ cm}^2/\text{sterad}^4$$

This is a small but relevant correction ($\approx 0.86\%$) and may become even a drastic one in view of the significance of the correction as the energy increases. Thus if we consider a frankly high-energy electron of about 1 MeV, we obtain a really relevant correction of about 1.7 times bigger.

³ In the units here introduced $r_e = \frac{e^2}{4\pi m_e} = \frac{\alpha}{m_e}$

⁴ $s_1 \simeq 4s_{0.5}$

Conclusion

This study presents a small but meaningful improvement over the traditional Klein-Nishina formula by including QED self-energy corrections. The logarithmic factor introduces a higher-order refinement, particularly relevant at higher electron energies, without significantly altering the results at lower energies. It may provide an enhanced theoretical foundation for understanding Compton scattering in contexts where QED effects play a role, such as high-energy astrophysics or particle physics experiments. In the previous section, we produced an estimate of the corrections relevant to electrons with an energy of 1 MeV. Although electrons at 1 MeV are clearly in a very different energy regime from that observed in graphene or other interesting materials with high velocity electrons, the one-loop corrections we calculated could be relevant even at lower energies, before reaching the full relativistic regime. This suggests that the corrections we introduce could offer useful insight even in contexts where electrons, although not relativistic, reach very high velocities, as in graphene.

Acknowledgment

This work was carried out through a collaboration between a physicist with a longstanding passion for the subject and an intelligent machine. The combination of human insight, theoretical understanding, and AI-assisted computational capabilities allowed for a detailed exploration of QED corrections to the Klein-Nishina formula. This effort underscores

how AI can complement traditional scientific methods, enabling deeper analysis and verification of complex physical processes.

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